

LARGE-SIGNAL MODELING AND SIMULATION OF INJECTION-TYPE PHASE SHIFTERS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction
2. Electronic Modeling
3. Electro-optical Modeling
4. Subsequent work
5. Conclusion

Further details available in the backup slides

INTRODUCTION

1

1 Introduction

Electro-optical Si Phase Shifters

- General functionality:
 - Electrical signal applied
 - Optical phase changes accordingly

1 Introduction

Electro-optical Si Phase Shifters

■ General functionality:

- Electrical signal applied
- Optical phase changes accordingly

■ Applications:

- Electro-optical transmitters
 - Mach-Zehnder modulators
 - Ring resonator modulators
- Sensors
- ...

Introduction

Electronic Modeling

Electro-optical Modeling

Subsequent work

Conclusion

1 Introduction

Si Phase Shifter Types

- PN-junction phase shifter:
 - Doped Si waveguide
 - Free carrier plasma dispersion effect
 - $\Delta n_{eff} \propto q$
 - $\Delta \alpha \propto q$
 - Charge carrier density change causes phase shift

T. Schwabe et al. "Forward-Biased Silicon Phase Shifter Modeling for Electronic-Photonic Co-Simulation and Validation in a 250 nm EPIC BiCMOS Technology," in Journal of Lightwave Technology, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 255-270, 1 Jan.1, 2025, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2024.3450949

a) Depletion-type phase shifter:

- Most commonly used
- Reverse-biased operation ($v_D < 0$)
- Efficiency scales with length $\rightarrow V_\pi L$ metric

b) Injection-type phase shifter:

- Forward-biased operation ($v_D > \phi_J$)
- High efficiency, low bandwidth

1 Introduction

Motivation

- Why using Injection-Type Phase Shifters?
 - High efficiency
 - Low bandwidth
 - Short
 - Equalizer circuits applicable
 - Increase bandwidth at the costs of efficiency
 - Similar performance as Depletion-Type Phase Shifters
 - But **much smaller** & linear!
 - Multiple modulators in one EPIC
 - Parallelization
 - Complex systems in 1 EPIC

ELECTRICAL MODELING

2

2 Electrical Modeling PN-junction

- Minority charge carrier injection

- Shockley equation follows:

$$i_D = I_S \cdot \left(e^{\frac{v_D}{V_T}} - 1 \right)$$

- Diffusion charges follow:

$$\Delta q_D = \tau_{TT} \cdot i_D$$

- Charges “stored” → diffusion capacitance:

$$C_d = \frac{d\Delta q_D}{dv_D} = \tau_{TT} \cdot \frac{1}{r_D}$$

- Recombination or high-injection currents

$$n_D \neq 1 \rightarrow i_D = I_S \cdot \left(e^{\frac{v_D}{n_D \cdot V_T}} - 1 \right)$$

Adapted from: S. M. Sze, M.-K. Lee, Semiconductor Devices Physics and Technology, p.64 Third. 605 Third Avenue, New York, NY 10158-0012: John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 2012, isbn: 978-0470-53794-7.

Introduction

Electronic Modeling

Electro-optical Modeling

Subsequent work

Conclusion

2 Electrical Modeling

Electronic Parasitics

- Contact resistance, ohmic semiconductor resistance: R_S
- Contact inductance: L_S
 - Short PS → Not negligible in IT-PS
- Substrate capacitance: C_{an} & C_{ca}
- Substrate resistance: R_{sub}

- Optional, less effective:
 - Sidewalls, impurities → Shunt resistance $G_{min} = \frac{1}{R_{sh}}$
 - Intercontact capacitance C_{con}

ELECTRO-OPTICAL MODELING

3

3 Electro-optical Modeling

Electro-optical Equivalent Circuit

- Static losses α_0 and phase shift φ_0 :

- Waveguide

- Dynamic losses $\Delta\alpha$ and phase shift $\Delta\varphi$:

- $\Delta q_D = \tau_{TT} \cdot i_D$

- $\Delta n_{eff} = f(\Delta q_D)$

- $\Delta\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \cdot \Delta n_{eff} \cdot l_{PS}$

- Free carrier plasma dispersion effect

- Charges Δq_D affect n_{eff} and α

- Charge-to- $\Delta\varphi$ converter

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$\Delta n_{eff} = f(\Delta q_D)$ required

Introduction

Electronic Modeling

Electro-optical Modeling

Subsequent work

Conclusion

3 Electro-optical Modeling

Free Carrier Plasma Dispersion Effect (1)

- Refractive index & attenuation constant change:

- Homogeneous charge density change $\Delta N_h, \Delta N_e$ assumed
- Only refractive index of Si n_{Si} changed (not n_{eff} of PS)

$$\Delta n = -\frac{e^2 \cdot \lambda_0^2}{8 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot c_0^2 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot n} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta N_e}{m_e^*} + \frac{\Delta N_h}{m_h^*} \right)$$

$$\Delta \alpha = \frac{e^2 \cdot \lambda_0^2}{4 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot c_0^2 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot n} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta N_e}{m_e^{*2} \cdot \mu_e} + \frac{\Delta N_h}{m_h^{*2} \cdot \mu_h} \right)$$

R. Soref, B. Bennett, "Electrooptical effects in silicon," IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 123–129, 1987. doi: 10.1109/JQE.1987.1073206.

- Spatial distribution of $\Delta N_h(x), \Delta N_e(x)$ has to be respected

- Optical mode centered in rib
- Charges distributed in rib
- Respected via overlap integral:

$$\Delta n_{eff} \approx \int_{A_m} \Delta n(x, y) \cdot \left| \frac{E(x, y)}{E_0} \right|^2 dA$$

- Rasigade, G., Marris-Morini, D., Ziebell, M., Cassan, E., Vivien, L.: Analytical model for depletion-based silicon modulator simulation. Opt. Express 19(5), 3919–3924 (2011) <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.19.003919>.
- Schermer, R.T., Bucholtz, F., Villarruel, C.A., Gil, J.G., Andreadis, T.D., Williams, K.J.: Investigation of electrooptic modulator disruption by microwave-induced transients. Opt. Express 17(25), 22586–22602 (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.17.022586>

3 Electro-optical Modeling

Free Carrier Plasma Dispersion Effect (2)

■ Calculation:

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \cdot \Delta n_{eff} \cdot l_{PS}$$

$$\Delta n_{eff} \approx \int_{A_m} \Delta n(x, y) \cdot \left| \frac{E(x, y)}{\tilde{E}_0} \right|^2 dA$$

$$\Delta n = -\frac{e^2 \cdot \lambda_0^2}{8 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot c_0^2 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot n} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta N_e}{m_e^*} + \frac{\Delta N_h}{m_h^*} \right)$$

$$\Delta \alpha = \frac{e^2 \cdot \lambda_0^2}{4 \cdot \pi^2 \cdot c_0^2 \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot n} \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta N_e}{m_e^{*2} \cdot \mu_e} + \frac{\Delta N_h}{m_h^{*2} \cdot \mu_h} \right)$$

- Rasigade, G., Marris-Morini, D., Ziebell, M., Cassan, E., Vivien, L.: Analytical model for depletion-based silicon modulator simulation. Opt. Express 19(5), 3919–3924 (2011)
- Schermer, R.T., Bucholtz, F., Villarruel, C.A., Gil, J.G., Andreadis, T.D., Williams, K.J.: Investigation of electrooptic modulator disruption by microwave-induced transients. Opt. Express 17(25), 22586–22602 (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1364/OE.17.022586>

R. Soref, B. Bennett, "Electrooptical effects in silicon," IEEE Journal of Quantum Electronics, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 123–129, 1987. doi: 10.1109/JQE.1987.1073206.

Charge carrier density distribution:

$$\Delta N_h = \begin{cases} p_{no} \cdot \left(e^{\frac{v_D}{V_T}} - 1 \right) \cdot e^{-\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_p \cdot \tau_p}}} & , x \geq x_c \\ 0 & , x < x_c \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta N_e = \begin{cases} n_{po} \cdot \left(e^{\frac{v_D}{V_T}} - 1 \right) \cdot e^{\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_n \cdot \tau_n}}} & , x \leq x_c \\ 0 & , x > x_c \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta q_D = |\Delta q_{D,h}| = |\Delta q_{D,e}|$$

$$|\Delta q_{D,h}| = \int_{A_{m,n}} \Delta N_h(x) dA$$

$$|\Delta q_{D,e}| = \int_{A_{m,p}} \Delta N_e(x) dA$$

TE Mode approximation:

$$\mathbf{E} = E_0(x, y) \cdot e^{j\omega t} \cdot e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \cdot (n_{eff,0} + \Delta n_{eff}) \cdot z} \cdot e^{-\frac{(\alpha_0 + \Delta \alpha) \cdot z}{2}}$$

$$E_0(x, y) \approx \begin{cases} \tilde{E}_0 \cdot \cos\left(\pi \cdot \frac{x}{d_m}\right) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{y-y_0}{y_0}\right) & , |x| \leq \frac{d_m}{2} \text{ and } 0 \leq y \leq y_0 \\ \tilde{E}_0 \cdot \cos\left(\pi \cdot \frac{x}{d_m}\right) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{y-y_0}{h_{PS}-y_0}\right) & , |x| \leq \frac{d_m}{2} \text{ and } y_0 \leq y \leq h_{PS} \\ 0 & , \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Introduction

Electronic Modeling

Electro-optical Modeling

Subsequent work

Conclusion

3 Electro-optical Modeling

Free Carrier Plasma Dispersion Effect (3)

- Result for fundamental TE-mode:

$$\Delta n_{eff} = \Delta n_{eff,h} + \Delta n_{eff,e} \approx -\frac{\Delta q_D}{2 \cdot d_m \cdot h_{PS} \cdot l_{PS} \cdot e} \cdot \underbrace{\left(\frac{\int_{x_c}^{\frac{d_m}{2}} e^{-\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_p \cdot \tau_p}}} \cdot \cos^2\left(\pi \cdot \frac{x}{d_m}\right) dx}{N_{h,n1} \cdot \int_{x_c}^{\frac{w_{PS}}{2}} e^{-\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_p \cdot \tau_p}}} dx} + \frac{\int_{\frac{d_m}{2}}^{x_c} e^{-\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_n \cdot \tau_n}}} \cdot \cos^2\left(\pi \cdot \frac{x}{d_m}\right) dx}{N_{e,n1} \cdot \int_{\frac{w_{PS}}{2}}^{x_c} e^{-\frac{x-x_c}{\sqrt{D_n \cdot \tau_n}}} dx} \right)}_{\approx \text{independent on } v_D}$$

- Effective refractive index change is **dominated by** $\Delta q_D(v_D)$ (total amount)
- Effect of change in spatial distribution is negligible

Different to DT-PS!

- $\Delta \varphi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_0} \cdot \Delta n_{eff} \cdot l_{PS}, \quad \Delta n_{eff} \propto \frac{\Delta q_D}{l_{PS}} \quad \Rightarrow \Delta \varphi \propto \Delta q_D \quad \Rightarrow \text{length-independent}$

- $\Delta \varphi \approx \pi \cdot \frac{\Delta q_D}{Q_\pi}$

3 Electro-optical Modeling

Electro-optical Equivalent Circuit (2)

- Static losses α_0 and phase shift φ_0 :

- Waveguide

- Dynamic losses $\Delta\alpha$ and phase shift $\Delta\varphi$:

- Charge-to- $\Delta\varphi$ converter

$$\Delta\varphi \approx \pi \cdot \frac{\Delta q_D}{Q_\pi} = \pi \cdot \frac{i_D \cdot \tau_{TT}}{Q_\pi}$$

$$\Delta\alpha \approx -\frac{\ln(2)}{l_{PS}} \cdot \frac{\Delta q_D}{Q_{3dB}} = -\frac{\ln(2)}{l_{PS}} \cdot \frac{i_D \cdot \tau_{TT}}{Q_{3dB}}$$

T. Schwabe et al. "Forward-Biased Silicon Phase Shifter Modeling for Electronic-Photonic Co-Simulation and Validation in a 250 nm EPIC BiCMOS Technology," in Journal of Lightwave Technology, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 255-270, 1 Jan.1, 2025, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2024.3450949

- Investigations on transit time:

- Voltage-dependent

$$\tau_{TT}(v_D) \approx \tau_{TT,0} + (\tau_{TT,on} - \tau_{TT,0}) \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{v_D - \varphi_J}{V_1}\right)$$

- Approximately constant for high bias voltages: $\tau_{TT}|_{v_D \gg \varphi_J} \approx \tau_{TT,on}$

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Subsequent work

Conclusion

SUBSEQUENT WORK

4

4 Subsequent Work After Modeling

1) Electro-optical measurement:

- Bias voltage swept
- Measured:
 - DC voltages & currents
 - Static optical power
 - Electro-optical S-Parameters

3) Model implementation

- Verilog-AMS
- SPICE compatible
- (EP)IC design flow compatible
- Reduction to optical envelope and center wavelength
- Electro-optical co-simulation

2) Parameter fitting

- Automated fitting
- Testbench in Keysight Advanced Design Systems
- Load measurement results
- Mimic measurement setup
- Model parameters optimized until measurement and simulation results are same

4) Equalizer & TX design

- Increase bandwidth
- Linearization
- Passive equalizer⁺
- Novel active equalizer^{*}

⁺ S. Tanaka and Y. Sobu, "High-speed silicon photonic modulator based on forward-biased PIN diodes and passive equalizers," 2020 *European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC)*, Brussels, Belgium, 2020, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ECOC48923.2020.9333260.
^{*}T. Schwabe, C. Kress, B. Sadiye, S. Kruse and J. Christoph Scheytt, "Analysis and Design of Forward Biased Silicon Photonics Phase Shifter Equalizer Circuits," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 192433-192450, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3629385.

CONCLUSION

5

5 Conclusion

Summary

- Derivation of an electro-optical IT-PS equivalent circuit:
 - pn-junction modeling
 - Electronic parasitics
 - Static photonic modeling
 - Dynamic electronic-photonic modeling
- Free carrier plasma dispersion effect modeling:
 - Change in spatial distribution of charge carriers is negligible
 - Phase shift (and attenuation):
 - $\Delta\varphi \approx \pi \cdot \frac{\tau_{TT}}{Q\pi} \cdot i_D$ and $\Delta\alpha \approx -\frac{\ln(2)}{l_{PS}} \cdot \frac{\tau_{TT}}{Q_{3dB}} \cdot i_D$
 - proportional to diode current
 - length-independent
 - Transit time is approximately constant for high bias voltages $\tau_{TT}|_{V_D \gg \varphi_J} \approx \tau_{TT,on}$
- Accurate IT-PS modeling + equalization:
 - Very compact, linear, high bandwidth transmitters

Further Details

EQUALIZATION

A detailed microchip layout is shown on the right side of the slide. The layout is rendered in a dark teal color with a fine grid pattern. It features various components, including two large octagonal structures at the bottom, several smaller rectangular blocks, and a complex network of lines representing circuit traces. The label 'A1' is prominently displayed in white, bold, sans-serif font in the upper right quadrant of the chip layout.

A1

A1 Equalization

Passive equalization – bandwidth extension

- PS small-signal equivalent circuit:

- Diode replaced by small-signal resistance $r_d = \left. \frac{dv_D}{di_D} \right|_Q = \frac{n_D \cdot V_T}{I_S} \cdot e^{-\frac{v_D}{n_D \cdot V_T}}$

- Simplification:

- Parasitic inductance & substrate capacitance neglected

- Passive equalizer:

- RC-filter in series to PS
- Diode pole compensated by RC-filter
- Ideal sizing of RC-filter: $R_{EQ} \cdot C_{EQ} = r_d \cdot C_d = \tau_{TT}$
- $f_{-3dB} \approx \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{r_d \cdot C_d} \cdot \frac{R_{EQ}}{r_{drv} + R_S}$
- Bandwidth extended at the costs of efficiency**

$$R_{EQ} = \eta \cdot r_d$$

$$C_{EQ} = \frac{C_d}{\eta}$$

A1 Equalization

Passive equalization – linearity

- Phase shift:

- $\Delta\varphi \approx \pi \cdot \frac{v_{TT}}{Q\pi} \cdot i_D$

- Phase shifter current:

- DC, for $R_{EQ} \gg r_d$:
$$I_D = \frac{V_{DRV}}{R_{EQ} + R_S + r_d} \approx \frac{V_{DRV}}{R_{EQ} + R_S}$$

 $\Rightarrow I_D \approx \text{linear}$

- R_{EQ} in 500 Ω to 50 $k\Omega$ range
+ Sufficient biasing: $r_d \ll 10 \Omega$
 \Rightarrow fulfilled

- Linearity scales with R_{EQ}

T. Schwabe, C. Kress, B. Sadiye, S. Kruse and J. Christoph Scheytt, "Analysis and Design of Forward Biased Silicon Photonics Phase Shifter Equalizer Circuits," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 192433-192450, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3629385.

A1 Equalization

Active equalization

- Negative feedback loop:
 - Virtual GND
 - Series resistance R_S compensated
- Passive equalizer:
 - $f_{-3dB} \approx \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{\tau_{TT,on}} \cdot \frac{R_{EQ}}{r_{drv} + R_S}$
- Active equalizer:
 - $f_{-3dB} \approx \frac{1}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{\tau_{TT,on}} \cdot \frac{R_{EQ}}{r_{drv}}$
- Bandwidth only limited by the driver!

T. Schwabe, C. Kress, B. Sadiye, S. Kruse and J. Christoph Scheytt, "Analysis and Design of Forward Biased Silicon Photonics Phase Shifter Equalizer Circuits," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 192433-192450, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3629385.

A1 Equalization

Active equalization - linearity

- Phase shift:

- $\Delta\varphi \approx \pi \cdot \frac{\tau_{TT}}{Q\pi} \cdot i_D$

- Phase shifter current:

- For $A \rightarrow -\infty$:
 single-ended $i_D = \frac{V_{DRV} - V_{Amp,IN}}{Z_{drv} + Z_{EQ}} - I_{IN} + \frac{\Delta v_{drv}}{2 \cdot (Z_{drv} + Z_{EQ})}$
 differential: $\Delta i_D = \frac{\Delta v_{drv}}{Z_{drv} + Z_{EQ}}$

Full linearity!

- Linearity scales with R_{EQ} and A

T. Schwabe, C. Kress, B. Sadiye, S. Kruse and J. Christoph Scheytt, "Analysis and Design of Forward Biased Silicon Photonics Phase Shifter Equalizer Circuits," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 192433-192450, 2025, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3629385.

MEASUREMENT SETUP

A microscopic image of a photonic quantum circuit chip, showing a complex network of waveguides, couplers, and phase shifters. The chip is divided into two main sections, with the label 'A2' overlaid on the right side. The image is rendered in a teal color scheme.

A2

A2 Measurement setup

Challenges, DUT

- 1) Large diffusion capacitance C_d
 - Far away from impedance matching
 - Low bandwidth
 - Low signal level at high frequencies
 - Flexible equalizer ($C_{EQ}(V_{CTRL})$) used
 - Optical amplifier used

- 2) Electro-optical measurement
 - Avoid coherent measurement
 - Measure amplitude instead of phase
 - Modulator structure used

- Measurement over large frequency range
- TX operation range covered
- Accurate τ_{TT} measurement

A2 Measurement setup

Overview

- Alignment structures
 - Automated coupling optimization
 - Static optical power measured
 - Bias voltage swept
 - Bias current measured
 - Static loss measured
 - Electro-optical S-Parameter measured
- in each step

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A2 Measurement setup

Lab

- Alignment structures
- Automated coupling optimization
- Static optical power measured
- Bias voltage swept
 - Bias current measured
 - Static loss measured
 - Electro-optical S-Parameter measured in each step

T. Schwabe et al. "Forward-Biased Silicon Phase Shifter Modeling for Electronic-Photonic Co-Simulation and Validation in a 250 nm EPIC BiCMOS Technology," in Journal of Lightwave Technology, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 255-270, 1 Jan. 1, 2025, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2024.3450949

A2 Measurement setup

Passive equalization

- Passive equalizer:
 - RC-filter in series to PS
 - Diode pole compensated by RC-filter
 - Ideal sizing of RC-filter: $R_{EQ} \cdot C_{EQ} = r_d \cdot C_d = \tau_{TT}$

- Variable capacitance C_{EQ} :
 - Tune until flat response $\rightarrow \tau_{TT} = R_{EQ} \cdot C_{EQ}$

DETAILS ON AUTOMATED PARAMETER FITTING

A detailed microchip image showing a complex circuit layout with various components and connections. The image is overlaid with a semi-transparent teal color. The label 'A3' is prominently displayed in the center-right area of the chip.

A3

A3 Parameter fitting

Challenge

- Many parameters:

- High complexity
- Limited computation power
- Separated fitting

- 1) Static electronic fitting $I_{IN,1}(V_{BIAS,1}, V_{BIAS,2})$
 $I_{IN,2}(V_{BIAS,1}, V_{BIAS,2})$
- 2) Static photonic fitting $P_{OUT}(V_{BIAS,1} = V_{BIAS,2} = 0, v_{S,1} = v_{S,2} = 0)$
- 3) Static electro-optical $P_{OUT}(V_{BIAS,1}, V_{BIAS,2}, v_{S,1} = v_{S,2} = 0)$
- 4) Dynamic electro-optical $S_{31}(V_{BIAS,1}, V_{BIAS,2}, v_{S,1}, v_{S,2}, f)$
 $S_{32}(V_{BIAS,1}, V_{BIAS,2}, v_{S,1}, v_{S,2}, f)$

- Static parameters determined independently of other measurements
- Complexity greatly reduced

A3 Parameter fitting

Automatization

- Keysight ADS
- Testbench:
 - Mimic Measurement setup in lab
- Load Measurement results
- Optimizer:
 - Automatically fit until simulation result matches measurements

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MODEL IMPLEMENTATION

A4

A4 Model implementation

Electro-optical co-simulation

■ Problem:

- $f_{opt} \gg f_{el}$
- Very short time steps in transient simulations
- Many time steps to resolve electrical signals
- High computation power required

■ Solution:

- Only optical envelope simulated
- Center frequency \rightarrow variable
- $E = E_0 \cdot e^{-j\omega_0 t} \rightarrow E_0, \omega_0$

A4 Model implementation

Verilog-AMS (1)

- Hardware-Description-Language:

- SPICE compatible → Simulations
- Linking to layout files via parameters
- Fully integrable in (EP)IC design flow

- Disciplines and natures:

- Every signal assigned to a discipline
- New discipline defined for optical signals

- Reduction to optical envelope & center wavelength

- Optical signal = Vector signals

- $E = E_0 \cdot e^{-j\omega_0 t} \rightarrow E_S = \begin{bmatrix} \Re\{E\} \\ \Im\{E\} \\ \omega_0 \end{bmatrix}$

Name	Potential	Flow	Domain
Logic	-	-	discrete
Electrical	Voltage	Current	continuous
Voltage	Voltage	-	continuous
Current	-	Current	continuous
Magnetic	Magneto Motive Force	Flux	continuous
Thermal	Temperature	Power	continuous
Kinematic	Position	Force	continuous
Kinematic Velocity	Velocity	Force	continuous
Rotational	Angle	Angular Force	continuous
Rotational Velocity	Angular Velocity	Angular Force	continuous
Photonic	Electric field	-	continuous
Electric Charge	charge	-	continuous

A4 Model implementation

Verilog-AMS (2)

- Linear R, C, L: Standard cell library
- Verilog-AMS models:
 - Waveguide
 - Charge-to- $\Delta\varphi$ converter
 - Diffusion capacitance (non-linear capacitor)


```

`include "constants.vams"
`include "disciplines.vams"
`include "../discipline_photonics/optoconstants.vams"
`include "../discipline_photonics/optodef.vams"
`include "../discipline_charge/chargedef.vams"

module Q_to_phi_conversion(opt_in, opt_out, Q_j, Q_diff);
  input [0:2] opt_in;
  input Q_j, Q_diff;
  output [0:2] opt_out;

  photonics [0:2] opt_in, opt_out;
  electric_charge Q_j, Q_diff;

  parameter real length = 400u from [0:inf];
  ...
  parameter real Q_pi = 5e-12 from (0:inf);
  real IL_dB_TE;
  ...
  real Q_in_tot;

  analog begin
    EFre_in = EF(opt_in[0]);
    wavelength_in = EF(opt_in[2]);
    ...
    phase_shift_rad = `M_PI*Q_in / Q_pi;
    phase_out_rad = phase_in_rad + phase_shift_rad;
    ...
    EAmplitude_out = EAmplitude_in*sqrt(10**(-(IL_dB_TE+delta_alpha_TE)/10));
    EFre_out = absdelay(EAmplitude_out*cos(f_phasete_out_rad), t_delay_TE);
    EFim_out = absdelay(EAmplitude_out*sin(f_phasete_out_rad), t_delay_TE);
    ...
    EF(opt_out[0]) <+ EFre_out;
    EF(opt_out[1]) <+ EFim_out;
    EF(opt_out[2]) <+ wavelength_in;
  end
endmodule

```

Also possible:
Whole model in one Verilog-AMS component

COMPARISON DEPLETION- AND INJECTION-TYPE PHASE SHIFTERS

A5 Comparison Depletion- and Injection-Type Phase Shifters

Theoretical performance limits

- Simulation in Keysight ADS assuming:
 - Ideal amplifier circuits
 - Ideal transmission lines
- Phase shifter models:
 - Full large-signal models
 - Depletion-Type: $l = 4\text{mm}$, $V_{Bias} = -3\text{V}$
 - Injection-Type: $l = 4\text{mm}$, $I_{Bias} = 2\text{mA}$

A5 Comparison Depletion- and Injection-Type Phase Shifters

Comparison to state-of-the-art EPICs

	PE TX	AE TX	[1]	[2]	[3]
Technology	250 nm BiCMOS	250 nm BiCMOS	250 nm BiCMOS	250 nm BiCMOS	45 nm CMOS
PS biasing	FB	FB	RB	RB	RB
total PS length (mm)	0.4	0.4	1.9	6.24	3.6 ^b
f_{-3dB} (GHz)	36 sim.	39.2 sim.	41.7 sim. ^a 33.4 meas.	30 sim. 24 meas.	42 sim. ^a
input voltage (V)	0.4	0.4	3	0.4	not published
ER (dB)	2.9 (20 Gb/s)	3 (30 Gb/s)	3 (44 Gb/s)	10 (30 Gb/s)	3.8 ^c (112 Gb/s)
Max. data rate (NRZ) (Gb/s)	40	60	44	60	/
Max. data rate (PAM4) (Gb/s)	50	84	/	80	112 ^c
DC power consumption (W)	0.59	1.28	0.5	1.77	0.31 ^d
power efficiency (pJ/bit)	11.8	15.2	11.4	22.1	2.8 ^d
Footprint (mm ²)	2.07	2.44	5.6	5.06	not published

^aStrong frequency peaking > 3 dB included

^bCalculated according to the published half-wave voltage $V_{\pi} = 4.6$ V and the technology's process design kit (PDK) data

^cContinuous time linear equalizer and 5-tap feed forward equalizer applied to insert additional poles and correct data signal via external equipment

^dPower dissipation in the equalizer not included

[1]F. Iseini, M. Inac, A. Malignaggi, A. Peczek, and G. Kahmen, "Monolithically integrated optoelectronic transmitter based on segmented Mach-Zehnder modulator in EPIC 250 nm BiCMOS technology," in *Proc. IEEE 23rd Topical Meeting Silicon Monolithic Integr. Circuits RF Syst.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 51–54.

[2]C. Kress, T. Schwabe, H. Rhee, and J. C. Scheytt, "Compact, high-speed Mach-Zehnder modulator with on-chip linear drivers in photonic BiCMOS technology," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 64561–64570, 2024.

[3]T. Baehr-Jones et al., "Monolithically integrated 112 Gbps PAM4 optical transmitter and receiver in a 45 nm CMOS-silicon photonics process," *Opt. Exp.*, pp. 24926–24938, Jul. 2023.

TECHNOLOGY

A detailed microchip layout for the A6 processor, showing various functional blocks, interconnects, and peripheral components. The layout is presented in a dark teal color scheme.

A6

A6 Technology

Silicon photonics technology

■ Advantages:

- EPIC technology available
 - Electronics + photonics in one chip
 - No Chip-to-chip bonding costs
 - Less parasitics
- Commercially established technology
- Low-cost mass production
 - High yield
 - small form factor
 - scalability
- (low loss edge couplers)

■ Disadvantage:

- Less modulation efficiency (compared to other material platforms)

■ Disadvantages compensated by:

- Decreased costs
- Parallelization

■ EPIC Technologies:

- IHP SG25H5 BiCMOS
- Global Foundries SPCL0 45nm CMOS

Thank you for your attention

Contact

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